

ENHANCING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS: OBSTACLES, CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

L.T. Akhmedova

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Uzbekistan State World Languages University,
Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17290762>

Abstract. *The article examines key obstacles and challenges encountered in the process of enhancing the professional competence of foreign language teachers, with a particular focus on novice educators. Using the example of a practical training session conducted as part of professional development courses at the Uzbek State World Languages University, the study examines key issues such as inadequate methodological training, low student motivation, disciplinary violations, students' emotional reactions, and negative attitudes toward teachers. The article also provides recommendations for engaging students' attention, including varying intonation, using visualization, interesting facts, and active teaching methods. Special emphasis is placed on analyzing pedagogical case studies, which help identify common mistakes made by young teachers and propose solutions to overcome them. Based on situational case studies, categories of challenges are identified, and teachers' responses are evaluated with consideration for professionalism, emotional control, and pedagogical ethics. The article offers practical solutions to improve the effectiveness of teachers' professional development and enhance their interaction with students.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, teacher, professional competence, pedagogical challenges, approaches, methods, techniques, situations, case studies, professional development.*

INTRODUCTION. The modern world demands that foreign language teachers not only possess deep language proficiency but also continuously enhance their professional competencies. Despite its importance, this process is fraught with numerous obstacles that can hinder teachers' professional growth. This issue is explored through a practical training session with foreign language teachers undergoing professional development at the Uzbek State World Languages University. Due to the article's scope limitations, not all challenges in enhancing professional competencies can be addressed. Therefore, this study focuses on key difficulties faced by teachers, particularly novice educators, and proposes solutions to ensure effective development of their professional skills. Additionally, it analyzes pedagogical case studies based on practical material. One of the primary challenges, in our view, is the lack of methodological training. Many teachers are insufficiently familiar with modern approaches, technologies, methods, techniques, and strategies for teaching foreign languages, leading to the use of traditional methodologies that reduce teaching effectiveness and professional competitiveness. Another significant challenge includes low student motivation, disciplinary issues, disruptive behavior, students' emotional reactions during classes, negative attitudes toward teachers or colleagues, and other related issues.

MAIN PART. During a practical training session dedicated to the obstacles and challenges in enhancing the professional competence of foreign language teachers, we analyzed issues such as barriers encountered in teaching, solutions to these barriers, common mistakes made by novice

teachers, and ways to address them, as well as the level of competence and creativity required to overcome challenges in pedagogical practice. A series of situational case studies were also addressed. The session began with an analysis of quotes from renowned scholars and writers:

- “A good teacher is not one who teaches well, but one who continues to learn” (folk wisdom).
- “A teacher affects eternity; you can never tell where their influence stops” (Henry Brooks Adams, American writer and historian, 1838–1918) [1].
- “Knowing how to make suppositions is the great art of a teacher” (Henri-Frédéric Amiel, Swiss writer, poet, and essayist, 1821–1881) [3].

Next, we analyzed the obstacles and challenges in enhancing the professional competence of foreign language teachers, with each participant sharing their strategies for overcoming them. The following stage involved identifying methods to capture students’ attention, such as appearance, speech, intonation, and moments of silence. The following recommendations were proposed to teachers:

Vary intonation during the lesson. Changing intonation or speech tempo, raising or lowering the voice, signals to students the need to focus and emphasizes key material.

Visualize. Prepare a dramatic image related to the lesson topic. You may not need to comment—let the student initiate the dialogue.

Start the lesson with an interesting fact or quote.

Begin with a test. Inform students that you want to assess their existing knowledge on the topic; such a test sparks a desire to learn. Conduct a follow-up test at the end of the lesson and compare initial and final results to demonstrate progress and the importance of attentiveness.

Techniques for capturing attention. Addressing the audience. Start a presentation with an address such as “Dear friends,” “Ladies and gentlemen,” or “Esteemed colleagues.” Maintain eye contact and use appropriate humor.

How to engage the audience during a presentation? Ask questions, cite authoritative sources, tailor each presentation to the context, use vocal techniques, and provide real-life examples.

How to energize the audience? Use a joke, a funny story, or an interactive game. It is recommended to begin a presentation with the most critical points.

Subsequently, group work was conducted, involving the completion of case studies and the presentation of each group’s results. Teachers were presented with situational case studies:

Case Study 1. A first-year student performs poorly, does not engage in class, and responds to calls to study or listen by saying, “I don’t need this profession. I’ll enroll in a university to become a lawyer after this; my uncle has connections.” How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 2. Exhausted by constant noise, the teacher asks students, “Why do you come to the institute? Isn’t it to learn a profession?” The students reply in unison, “We come to socialize with friends!” How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 3. It’s the first lesson of the second year. One student is lying on the desk, half-asleep. The teacher asks, “What’s wrong with you? What time did you go to bed?” The student replies, “I went to bed late—3 or 4 a.m., I don’t remember.” The teacher asks, “What were you doing?” The student responds, “Playing online games.” How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 4. The teacher says, “Open your notebooks, start writing...” Noticing one student isn’t writing, the teacher asks, “Why aren’t you writing?” The student replies, “Why should I write? I’d rather listen carefully and memorize.” How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 5. A female student, learning that her friend sitting next to her scored one point higher on a test, considers the grade unfair. Out of resentment toward the teacher, she frowns, crosses her arms, pushes away her notebook and textbook, puts down her pen, and has tears in her eyes. When asked, “What’s wrong? Why aren’t you working?” she remains silent and does nothing. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 6. At the start of the lesson, the teacher distributes graded assignments and suggests working on corrections. One student notices an unchecked mistake and loudly announces it to the class. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 7. While writing on the board or presenting, the teacher makes a mistake. A student points it out publicly, noticed by the entire class. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 8. In the teacher’s presence, a student negatively comments on a colleague or another teacher. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 9. While teaching a new topic, one of the teacher’s phrases triggers inappropriate laughter among students. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 10. During a lesson, a student asks a question about the topic, but the teacher doesn’t know the answer. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 11. During the lesson, a note is passed from the back row. Students read it silently, look at the ceiling, giggle, and pass it on without hiding it from the teacher. The teacher takes the note, reads “Look at the ceiling,” looks up, and the class bursts into laughter. How should the teacher respond, and why?

Case Study 12. A young teacher asks a disruptive student, “Why aren’t you listening to me?” The student loudly responds, “Because I don’t like you.” How should the teacher respond, and why? [3].

Solutions to the Challenges in the Case Studies:

Case Study 1: Student claims the profession is unnecessary, planning to become a lawyer. Solution: The teacher can calmly explain that current studies develop universal skills, such as discipline and critical thinking, which are valuable in any profession, including law. An individual conversation can be offered to discuss the student’s goals and demonstrate the subject’s relevance to their future plans. This response respects the student’s choice, avoids conflict, and motivates by highlighting the practical value of education.

Case Study 2: Students say they come to socialize. Solution: The teacher can acknowledge the importance of socializing but emphasize that class time is for learning, with socializing better suited for breaks. Interactive methods, such as group tasks, can combine their interest in socializing with academic activities. This redirects students’ energy constructively, maintains discipline, and sustains engagement.

Case Study 3: Student is sleepy due to late-night gaming. Solution: The teacher can gently remind the student of the importance of a proper sleep schedule for academic success and health, encouraging participation with a simple question. A later discussion on time management can follow. This gentle approach respects the student, avoids public shaming, and addresses the issue.

Case Study 4: Student refuses to write, preferring to listen. Solution: The teacher can explain that note-taking helps structure and retain information but allow the student to try their method if it doesn’t disrupt others. An alternative, such as brief digital notes, can be suggested. This demonstrates flexibility and respect for individual learning styles while emphasizing active engagement.

Case Study 5: Student is upset over a lower grade. Solution: The teacher can approach the student after class for a private conversation to understand her reaction, explain grading criteria, and offer help to improve (e.g., an extra assignment). This individual approach reduces emotional tension, rebuilds trust, and motivates further effort.

Case Study 6: Student publicly points out the teacher's grading mistake. Solution: The teacher thanks the student for their attentiveness, corrects the mistake, and uses the situation to highlight the importance of thoroughness. For example: "Thank you for noticing; it reminds us to be diligent." This preserves the teacher's authority, shows openness to feedback, and turns the mistake into a learning opportunity.

Case Study 7: Student points out a mistake on the board. Solution: The teacher thanks the student, corrects the mistake, and emphasizes that student attentiveness improves the lesson. For example: "Great catch, thank you—let's fix it." This demonstrates professionalism, collaboration, and strengthens classroom trust.

Case Study 8: Student criticizes a colleague. Solution: The teacher can state that such comments are inappropriate and redirect focus to the lesson. For example: "Let's respect all teachers and focus on our topic." If repeated, the issue can be discussed with a group advisor. This upholds professional ethics, prevents conflict, and maintains a respectful atmosphere.

Case Study 9: Teacher's phrase causes laughter. Solution: The teacher can smile calmly, acknowledge the humor (e.g., "Looks like I said something funny!"), and redirect attention to the lesson with a task. This diffuses the situation, maintains control, and avoids awkwardness.

Case Study 10: Teacher doesn't know the answer to a question. Solution: The teacher can honestly say, "That's an interesting question; I'll look it up and address it next class." Then, they research and provide the answer later. Honesty builds trust, and following through demonstrates responsibility and professionalism.

Case Study 11: Students laugh over a prank note. Solution: The teacher can smile and say, "Nice joke, but let's get back to the lesson to make the most of our time." A post-lesson discussion on respectful behavior can follow. This light response maintains a positive atmosphere while reinforcing discipline.

Case Study 12: Student says they don't like the teacher. Solution: The teacher can calmly respond, "I'm sorry you feel that way, but let's focus on learning. I'm here to help with any questions." A private conversation can be offered later to understand the issue. This calm response preserves professionalism, avoids escalation, and shows openness to dialogue.

After addressing the situational case studies, teachers collectively identified the types of challenges they face in teaching and analyzed their possible responses and reasons. Challenges were categorized, and teachers' reactions were evaluated based on professionalism, emotional control, and pedagogical ethics.

At the reflection stage, the poem "Do Not Dare Forget the Teachers" by Andrei Dementev was presented, highlighting the teacher's vital role in students' lives, their care, and their contribution to student success.

Listening to the poem helps students recognize the value of teachers' efforts and the need to show respect and gratitude.

The text evokes an emotional response, focusing on teachers' feelings as they await news from students and rejoice in their achievements, fostering empathy and reflection on human relationships. The poem also encourages gratitude and respect for teachers, cultivating qualities like responsibility and appreciation.

Types of Teachers' Challenges

Challenge Type	Case Study Examples	Description	Cause
Low student motivation	Case Studies 1, 2, 3, 4	Students show disinterest in the subject or profession, prioritizing socializing, gaming, or alternative career plans. This reduces lesson effectiveness and requires engagement strategies.	Students may not see the subject's value, have other goals, or lack intrinsic motivation.
Disciplinary issues and disruptive behavior	Case Studies 2, 9, 11, 12	Noise, giggling, passing notes, provocative comments, or defiance disrupt the learning process, requiring group management and discipline.	Students may be bored, seeking attention, or testing boundaries.
Students' emotional reactions	Case Studies 5, 12	Students display resentment, dissatisfaction, or personal dislike due to grades, comparisons, or attitudes toward the teacher, creating classroom tension.	Emotional immaturity, perceived unfair grading, or personal conflicts.
Teacher's mistakes and students' reactions	Case Studies 6, 7, 10	Teachers may err in grading, board work, or answering questions. Publicly pointed out by students, this puts the teacher in a vulnerable position.	Human error, student pressure, or inadequate preparation.
Negative attitudes toward teachers or colleagues	Case Studies 8, 12	Students openly criticize the teacher or colleagues, potentially undermining authority and creating conflict.	Personal dislike, attention-seeking, or lack of respect for authority.

In the context of our professional development session at the Uzbek State World Languages University, the poem served as a starting point for discussing teachers' professional challenges, such as lack of student feedback or indifference, and exploring solutions.

*Do not dare forget the teachers.
They worry about us and remember.
In the quiet of their thoughtful rooms,
They await our return and news.
They miss these infrequent meetings.
And no matter how many years pass by,
The teacher's happiness comes to be
From our students' victories.
Yet we are sometimes so indifferent to them:
No New Year's greetings sent their way.*

*In our haste or simply out of laziness,
We don't write, don't visit, don't call.
They wait for us. They watch over us,
Rejoicing every time for those
Who somewhere pass another test
Of courage, honesty, and success.
Do not dare forget the teachers.
Let your life be worthy of their efforts [4].*

CONCLUSION. The analysis of the outlined problem leads to the conclusion that the challenges faced by teachers include low student motivation, disciplinary issues, emotional reactions, teacher errors, and negative attitudes toward teachers or colleagues. Teachers' responses should be professional, flexible, and focused on maintaining a respectful atmosphere and effective learning environment. Key qualities in such situations include emotional control, the ability to connect with students, and the capacity to turn challenges into opportunities for learning and strengthening authority.

REFERENCES

1. Adams, Henry. (2002). The Education of Henry Adams. In: Bartlett, John. Bartlett's Familiar Quotations. 17th ed. Boston: Little, Brown and Company.
2. Akhmedova, L. T., Lagay, E. A. (2016). Modern Technologies in Teaching Russian Language and Literature. Tashkent.
3. Amiel, Henri-Frédéric. In: The Quotable Teacher (2003). Edited by Randy Howe. Guilford, CT: Lyons Press.
4. Dementev, A. D. (2006). Poems. Moscow.